

Probiotics -The Future of Bacteriotherapy in Endodontics: A Review

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Received on: 15 September 2024; Accepted on: 20 September 2024; Published on : 20 October 2024

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Abstract

Endodontics is a dental specialty focused on preventing, diagnosing, and treating conditions affecting the dental pulp and the tissues around the root of the tooth. The primary goal of endodontic treatment is to preserve the tooth's health and functionality for an extended period. Successful endodontic therapy depends on three key elements: thorough cleaning, effective disinfection of the root canals, and proper filling, with each component being crucial. The market for probiotic products, which contain viable bacteria with established health benefits, is rapidly expanding. While probiotics have traditionally been linked to gut health, recent research has explored their potential benefits for oral health. This review aims to investigate the mechanisms through which probiotic bacteria may influence oral health and to summarize the observed effects of probiotics in the context of oral care.

Keyword: Probiotics; Lactobacillus; Bifidobacterium; Poloxamer; E. faecalis; C. albicans; Endodontic infections;

Introduction

Periapical pathology refers to the inflammation and destruction of tissues surrounding the root of a tooth, typically resulting from pulpal inflammation or necrosis. In cases with necrotic pulp and diseased periapices, over 90% of the microflora consists of obligate anaerobes from genera such as Fusobacterium, Eubacterium, Prevotella, Porphyromonas, and Peptostreptococcus.^{1,2}

The success rate of endodontic treatments, which ranges from 86% to 98%, is determined by the resolution of clinical symptoms and radiological improvements of the treated tooth.³

A primary cause of endodontic failure is persistent or secondary intra-radicular microbiological infection.⁴ Microorganisms can coalesce and adhere to the radicular dentin, forming dense biofilms that maintain the infection. Inadequate disinfection protocols and poor coronal seals can lead to secondary infections, which may arise at any time after the initial treatment.^{5,6}

Studies by Pinheiro et al. have shown that Enterococcus faecalis is the most common microorganism found (45.8%) in root canals of previously treated teeth, followed by Parvimonas micra (24%), Fusobacterium (6.7%), and Propionibacterium (3.3%).⁷ Additionally, E. faecalis forms complex, well-organized biofilms in which

bacterial cells develop tolerance to higher antibiotic concentrations than required to eliminate planktonic cells.^{8,9}

Treatment strategies against E. faecalis include

A. Irrigants and Intracanal Medicaments:

These are used to enhance the outcome of endodontic therapy by reducing microbial load within the root canal system. Commonly used irrigants include saline, sodium hypochlorite, chlorhexidine, and EDTA. Sodium hypochlorite is a potent tissue solvent and antimicrobial agent, though it is highly toxic to periapical tissues. Chlorhexidine (CHX) provides broad-spectrum antimicrobial action with the added benefit of substantivity but is less effective as a tissue solvent. EDTA functions by chelating minerals and removing the smear layer when it comes into contact with the root canal walls.¹⁰

1% cetrimide and triple antibiotic paste were found to significantly reduce the viability of E. faecalis compared to chlorhexidine (CHX) and calcium

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How to cite this article: Chhabra et al. - Probiotics - The Future of Bacteriotherapy in Endodontics : A Review HTAJ OCD 2024

hydroxide.¹¹ [Jeison et al]

BioPure MTAD, which combines doxycycline, citric acid, and a detergent, was more effective against *E. faecalis* and *C. albicans*, showing significantly larger zones of microbial inhibition than 5.25% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) and 2% CHX.¹² [Davis et al]

B. Activation Methods During Irrigation:

Various techniques can enhance the effectiveness of irrigants, including sonic and ultrasonic activation, laser activation, and the photon-induced photoacoustic streaming (PIPS) technique. The photon-induced photoacoustic streaming (PIPS) technique produces powerful, successive shockwaves that deliver irrigants in a three-dimensional manner without raising the temperature.¹³ Laser-activated irrigation using an Er:YAG laser combined with the PIPS technique and sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) was more effective at removing *E. faecalis* biofilm from the root canal system compared to other activation methods, such as sonic and ultrasonic techniques.¹⁴ [Mohammed et al]

Phytomedicines are used for their anti-inflammatory, antibiotic, analgesic, and sedative properties, and as intracanal medicaments and irrigants in endodontics. Various herbal extracts, including aloe vera, neem, propolis, triphala, turmeric, passion fruit juice, tea tree oil, and *Morinda citrifolia* (noni), have been investigated for their antimicrobial properties and potential applications in endodontic treatment.¹⁵

Newer remedy- Probiotics are currently used which are live microorganisms that give health benefits to the host. The term "probiotic" was introduced by Lilley and Stillwell in 1965, and in 2002, the WHO defined probiotics as live microorganisms that, when administered in acceptable quantities, offer health benefits. While probiotics have been effectively used in drug, particularly for gastrointestinal diseases, they're also being explored in dentistry as a form of "relief remedy" to help and treat oral conditions.

Probiotics appear to serve through colonization resistance and modulation of bacteria. They've shown effectiveness in managing gingival inflammation, periodontal conditions, treating halitosis and candidal infections, and precluding dental caries.^{19,20}

Species Used as Probiotics

Lactic Acid- Producing Bacteria

Lactobacillus acidophilus, *Lactobacillus casei*, *Lactobacillus bulgaricus*, *Lactobacillus fermentum*, *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*, *Lactobacillus reuteri*, *Lactobacillus lactis*.

Non-Lactic Acid- Producing Bacteria

Enterococcus faecium, *Escherichia coli*, *Streptococcus thermophilus*, *Propionibacterium*. *Bifidobacterium* Species, *Bifidobacterium bifidum*, *Bifidobacterium adolescentis*, *Bifidobacterium longum*, *Bifidobacterium breve*.

Medium of Action

Probiotics work by resisting the colonization of pathogenic bacteria through competition for growth factors and nutrients. Probiotic species can alter the composition of biofilms and producing antimicrobial metabolites and enzymes that

target pathogens. They also modulate the pro-inflammatory cytokines, similar as IL-1 β , TNF- α , and IL-8, while adding the product of IgA and other anti-inflammatory mediators.²¹

Probiotic Delivery agents

Probiotics can be administered in several ways, including

- soyabean, fruit juices.
- Dairy Products Incorporated in milk and yoghurt.
- grounded foods (including yogurt, sour cream, and cheese).
- Lately, probiotics have been combined with Poloxamer 407, anion-ionic copolymer of polyethylene and polypropylene oxide, which is used as a gelatinizing agent including fluoridated dentifrices.

Concept of Probiotics in Endodontics

Traditionally, endodontics focuses on the complete eradication of all microorganisms within the root canal system still, due to the complex morphology of root canal, including multiple accessory canals achieving disinfection was difficult.

But studies have suggested that atleast a significant reduction in the bioload of microorganisms can be achieved. The current and arising trends to treat a microbial infection is to achieve and maintain a state of equilibrium within the human microbiome and to shift towards a more favorable ecology conducive of healing.²³ New conception of Bacteriotherapy in Endodontics is to replace the pathogenic bacteria by healthy bacteria.

Recent studies have explored the use of various *Lactobacillus* species as experimental probiotics. *Lactobacillus reuteri*, for instance, generates metabolites such as reuterin and reutericyclin, which act as broad-spectrum antimicrobial agents. These compounds inhibit the synthesis of microbial DNA, thereby preventing the formation of biofilms composed of both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, as well as fungi and protozoa.²⁵

Recently, researchers have isolated and characterized various oral lactic acid bacteria and bifidobacteria for their potential benefits in treating oral health issues such as caries, periodontal diseases, and halitosis.²⁶ In addition, studies have explored dairy strains to identify new oral probiotics. As the emerging probiotic products for oral health may feature different species from those currently available on the market. Preliminary findings have shown that a probiotic mouthwash containing three distinct oral streptococci can effectively reduce bacteria associated with dental caries and periodontitis.^{27,28}

Consumption of probiotic yogurt was found to significantly reduce the growth of *Streptococcus mutans* in saliva, potentially decreasing the incidence and severity of enamel demineralization in patients undergoing fixed orthodontic treatment.²⁹

A novel method involves using 30% Poloxamer 407 mixed with Man, Rogosa, and Sharpe (MRS) or Tryptic Soy Broth (TSB) to deliver probiotics into the root canal. Poloxamer 407, which forms gels at higher temperatures and aqueous solutions at lower temperatures (4°C), is considered an ideal delivery vehicle for intracanal medicaments.^{30,31}

A novel delivery system for probiotics into the root canal system employed a 30% solution of poloxamer 407 (Pluronic

F-127) mixed with MRS broth containing probiotics. Poloxamers are non-ionic, biocompatible copolymers of polyethylene oxide and polypropylene oxide, commonly used in pharmaceutical formulations as surfactants, emulsifiers, solubilizers, dispersants, and in vivo absorbance enhancers. Their inverse thermosensitivity is a key feature: they dissolve in aqueous solutions at low temperatures (around 4°C) but form a gel at higher temperatures. This property makes them particularly suitable as delivery vehicles for intra-canal treatments between clinical visits. Importantly, the study demonstrated that the colony counts (CFU/mL) of *E. faecalis* and *C. albicans* were significantly reduced using the tested probiotic formulation.^{30,31}

Another study assessed the antimicrobial effects of *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*, and *Bifidobacterium bifidum* against *E. faecalis* and *C. albicans* in both planktonic and biofilm forms. The results showed that all three probiotics exhibited antimicrobial activity, with lactobacilli showing a reduction in *C. albicans* colonies. The study also evaluated the use of 30% Poloxamer 407 as a delivery vehicle for probiotics in the root canal, finding that a poloxamer-based probiotic mixture could be maintained in the root canal for about a week, creating a more favorable environment for healing.³²

In a recent experiment, *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* was tested as an irrigant for treating post-endodontic infection caused by *E. faecalis*. Cultured in MRS broth and formulated in sterile water, this probiotic irrigant significantly reduced *E. faecalis* colonies within 24 hours of application, suggesting that *L. rhamnosus* could be an effective, natural, and safe probiotic irrigant when used with an appropriate vehicle.³³

Conclusion

The use of probiotics in endodontic therapy presents both challenges and potential benefits as a complementary antimicrobial treatment. Probiotics not only target endodontic pathogens but may also help prevent their re-colonization, reducing endodontic failures and improving the long-term success of root canal treatments. Poloxamer serves as a novel delivery method for probiotics into the root canal system. However, due to variations in strains, dosages, frequencies, and experimental methods, further in-vitro and in-vivo studies are necessary to better understand and validate the effectiveness of probiotics in endodontics and to establish evidence-based treatment protocols.

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